

Reaching bistability in a photochromic spirooxazine embedded sol–gel hybrid coatings

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Novel photochromic coatings were designed having a remarkable long-term stability of both the coloured state and colourless states in the dark (bistability). The coatings consist of a dispersion of a commercial spirooxazine in a functionalized sol–gel hybrid matrix, acquiring a deep purple coloration upon irradiation with UV-light. In order to stabilize the coloured form of the dye, a zinc salt, capable of forming a chelate with the photochromic molecule when irradiated, was incorporated into the matrix, resulting in a drastic reduction of the thermal bleaching kinetics. The coloured coatings can only be reverted to their original colourless state by irradiation with visible light. This recording–erasing process is reversible and can, therefore, be repeated by alternating irradiation with UV and visible light. Adding the bistable behaviour to the specific properties of reversible photochromic systems makes a new range of applications in the field of optics and light-controlling media available.

Introduction

Photochromism has attracted considerable attention owing to its potential application in various photoactive devices, such as optical memories, optical switches and non-linear optics.^{1–3} Among the different types of photochromic compounds, spirooxazines⁴ are of importance due to the high fatigue resistance of the photochromic dyes, which makes them interesting for a wide range of applications.¹ The irradiation of these molecules with UV-light results in a heterolytic cleavage of the C (sp³)–O bond of the oxazine ring, leading to the formation of coloured merocyanine forms, as shown in Fig. 1. The system reverts thermally or by irradiation with visible light to its original colourless form.^{1,4}

Over the last few decades, the application of spirooxazine in optical memories has been hindered by the short lifetime of the coloured merocyanine, which reverts thermally to the closed colourless spirooxazine.¹ Many studies of the ring-closing reaction dynamics have been performed and various methods of stabilizing the merocyanine form have been developed.^{5–9} However, the efficient storage of optical information using spirooxazine derivatives, which show high fatigue resistance, is a challenging issue. This is mainly due to the difficulty of stabilizing the coloured merocyanine form of the spirooxazine molecule to ensure that the colour can be maintained for a relatively long period of time. In addition, the fast bleaching process of the photochromic material makes it difficult to separate the reading, writing and erasing processes of an optical memory, as data can be erased by the light beam used for reading the information. Different approaches have been proposed to enhance the stability in terms of increasing the lifetime of the coloured form of the dye in the dark, such as the incorporation of suitable substituents in the appropriate positions of the structure of the photochromic molecule,¹⁰ or the selection of a suitable medium

Fig. 1 Colourless and coloured forms of the photochromic spirooxazine 1-propyl-3,3,5,6-tetramethyl-spiro[indoline-2,3'-quinolino]oxazine].

(e.g. polymeric matrix), which disfavours the decolouration process.^{11,12} Yuan *et al.*¹⁰ have reported a novel spironaphthoxazine molecule with a much more stable open-ring merocyanine form that allowed a successful 2D and 3D optical storage. The material consisted of a ferrocene derivative of a spirooxazine molecule dispersed in a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) matrix. Some authors have introduced a suitable coordinate group in the *ortho* position or other positions adjacent to the O atom of the oxazine in order to form a bidentate group that is able to link a metal ion (Ni, Zn or Co) to stabilize the coloured form in solution.^{13–15} Nishikiori and co-workers¹⁶ have studied the isomerization and zinc-chelation of spironaphthoxazine molecules in tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and octyl-modified TEOS systems, in terms of the effect of the sol–gel-xerogel transition on the intensity of the fluorescence signal and the excitation spectra of the photochromic molecule.

In this work, novel photochromic coatings, that acquire a purple coloration upon irradiation with UV-light, were designed having a remarkably stable coloured state in the dark that can only be reverted to the original colourless state by irradiation with visible light. The bistability of the photochromic system is of great importance for the application of the coatings in optical recording media. The coatings consist of the dispersion

of a commercial spirooxazine in a functionalized sol–gel hybrid matrix that together with the incorporation of a salt, which forms a chelate with the photochromic molecule, results in a drastic reduction of the thermal bleaching and, hence, in the remarkable stabilization of the coloured form of the dye.

Experimental

Preparation of the photochromic coatings

Samples were prepared from mixtures of tetraacetoxysilane (TAS), *p*-aminophenyl trimethoxysilane (NH₂PhTMOS), acetic acid (AcH) and water in a TAS : NH₂PhTMOS : AcH : H₂O molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 : 7. The sols were allowed to hydrolyze for 8 hours under stirring at 15 °C. The photochromic molecules and the zinc chloride were added as a THF solution after the hydrolysis of the sol, to give a photochromic dye to Si molar ratio of 2 : 200 and a photochromic molecules to zinc chloride molar ratio of 1 : 10. THF was used as the solvent due to the possibility of obtaining highly concentrated solutions and good miscibility with the coating sol. The deposition of the films was carried out after the addition of the dye using the spin-coating technique. The thickness of the samples was around 640 nm.

The concentration of the dye in the THF and EtOH solutions was adjusted to $7.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M. Ph-modified ormosil matrices were prepared with the same methodology used for the NH₂Ph-modified ormosil matrices, but using phenyl trimethoxysilane (PhTMOS) instead of NH₂PhTMOS.

Characterization

The photochromic samples were irradiated with a 365 nm, 100 W, B-100AP UV lamp from UVP, giving a UV-light intensity on the sample of 8.9 mW cm⁻². A dichroic 100 W halogen lamp was used as the irradiation source (visible light) for the bleaching of the coloured samples. The distance between the sample and the lamp was 20 cm. The thickness of the film was measured with a surface roughness measuring system—SurfTest SV-3000H4. The absorption spectra of the resulting films as well as the kinetics of the bleaching process were measured using a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The bleaching kinetics was monitored vs. time at the wavelength of the maximum absorption of each sample (visible range) at 20 °C. $t_{1/2}$ is defined as the time required by the sample to reach $D_{Abs_{max}}/2$ during the bleaching or darkening process.

The pore environment polarity in the organic–inorganic hybrid coating was determined by the $E_T(33)$ (2,6-dichloro-4-(2,4,6-triphenyl-*N*-pyridino)phenolate) polarity probe. The $E_T(30)$ and $E_T(33)$ scales can be interconverted according to the following equation: $E_T(30)$ (kcal mol⁻¹) \approx 0.979 $E_T(33)$ – 7.461.¹⁷ $E_T(30)$ is known as Reichardt's dye (2,6-diphenyl-4-(2,4,6-triphenyl-*N*-pyridino)phenolate).

IR spectra of the resulting samples were measured using a Perkin–Elmer FT-IR 1700X spectrophotometer, from polyethylene pellets in the 500–150 cm⁻¹ range.

Results and discussion

The usage of ormosil (organically modified silica) matrices for the entrapment of photochromic molecules has shown to be an

effective way to control the stabilization of the coloured or colourless forms of the photochromic molecule. The introduction of organic functional groups into the inner pore surface of the matrix allows the tailoring of the chemical environment where the photochromic molecules will be located, in terms of the effectiveness of the interaction between the molecules and the Si–OH groups on the surface of the pores.^{18,19} This interaction will have an important effect on the thermal stability of the different forms of the molecule in the embedding ormosil matrix.

The photochromic compound 1-propyl-3,3,5,6-tetramethylspiro[indoline-2,3⁰-(quinolino)oxazine] (shown in Fig. 1), used for the preparation of the different photochromic coatings, forms different coloured merocyanines when irradiated with UV-light (darkening). In order to stabilize the colour of the photochromic material, the coloured merocyanine forms of the dye molecule should be stabilized. The functionalization of the ormosil matrix with aminophenyl (NH₂Ph) groups resulted in an important increase of the lifetime of the coloured state of the samples after irradiation with UV-light. These NH₂Ph groups interact *via* hydrogen bonding with neighbouring amino groups or with residual silanols (Fig. 2). In the presence of water, which promotes the transfer of protons from silanols to amino groups, the surface acquires the character of a macroscopic zwitterion²⁰ and therefore, a very high polarity. This high polarity of the inner pore surface of the matrix promotes the stabilization of the coloured merocyanine forms of the dye,¹⁹ resulting in a much slower bleaching process as compared with the same molecules embedded in an ormosil matrix modified with Ph-groups or in THF and EtOH solutions (Fig. 3). The use of polymeric matrices to stabilize the merocyanine form of the spirooxazine^{11,12} is limited by the low stability of the matrix itself upon UV irradiation.²¹

The bleaching process in solution is faster in THF ($t_{1/2}$ (in the dark) \approx 20.4 s) than in EtOH ($t_{1/2}$ (in the dark) \approx 148 s), due to the higher

Fig. 2 Scheme of a pore in NH₂Ph-functionalized silica matrix where the photochromic molecules are located.

Fig. 3 Thermal bleaching of the photochromic spirooxazine in ormosil matrices and in solution (THF and EtOH).

polarity of the EtOH ($E_T(30) \approx 51.9$) as compared with that of the THF ($E_T(30) \approx 37.4$),²² which stabilizes the coloured merocyanine and slows down the bleaching process. The kinetic data of the different samples are summarized in Table 1. In ormosil matrices, the photochromic molecules show slower bleaching than in solution, due to the higher polarity of the pore environment where the dye molecules are located, being the $E_T(30)$ values of 57.6 and 54.6 kcal mol⁻¹ for NH₂Ph and Ph-modified matrices, respectively. The bleaching process of the photochromic molecules was found to be much slower in NH₂Ph-modified matrices than in matrices modified with Ph-groups, due to the interaction of the merocyanine with the pore surface *via* hydrogen bonding (Fig. 2).

Despite the important slow-down of the thermal bleaching process of the spirooxazine molecules in hybrid sol–gel matrices, the coloured state of the coatings is not stable enough for its application in optical memories. In order to further stabilize the coloured form of the photochromic dye, zinc ions were embedded together with the photochromic molecules in the NH₂Ph-modified ormosil matrix to chelate the coloured merocyanine molecules. The resulting thin films are optically transparent and acquire a purple coloration upon irradiation with UV light. The absorption spectra of the irradiated spirooxazine molecules in the NH₂Ph-modified ormosil matrix and in the same matrix in which zinc ions were incorporated is shown in Fig. 4.

The absorption band of the dye molecules in NH₂Ph-modified ormosil matrices shows a significant shift to the UV when zinc ions are present in the matrix. The photochromic molecules in

Fig. 4 UV-Vis spectra of the photochromic spirooxazine dye embedded in a NH₂Ph-modified ormosil matrix, with and without zinc ions.

their coloured state (merocyanine) can form a chelate with the zinc ions in which the pyranil O and imino N atoms act as coordinating groups.^{13,14} Only the open forms B and C of the coloured merocyanine could form chelates, taking into consideration the orientation of the hybrid sp² orbitals of the imino N and O atoms. No chelate can be formed from the colourless form in the dark.¹³ Fig. 5 shows the scheme of the formation, during UV irradiation, of a possible chelate of the spirooxazine with zinc ions with coordination number 4. This structure was confirmed using FTIR spectroscopy both in the presence and absence of Zn²⁺ ions. In the sample prepared with ZnCl₂, new bands are observed at 300 and 290 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to the $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{Cl})$ vibrations,²³ and bands at 251 and 420 cm⁻¹, which can be attributed to the $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{N}_{\text{imino}})$ and $\nu(\text{Zn}-\text{O}_{\text{pyranil}})$ vibrations, respectively.²³

The formation of a zinc chelate of the merocyanine form of the spirooxazine molecules prevented the thermal bleaching that occurs upon cessation of the irradiation with UV light, as observed in samples without zinc ions. The coloration acquired upon irradiation with UV-light is kept stable in the dark, allowing permanent recording of optical information in the coatings. Fig. 6 shows the thermal bleaching of the coloured merocyanine molecules in the dark in a NH₂Ph-modified ormosil matrix, and the stability obtained by the incorporation of zinc ions in the matrix, the bleaching kinetics data are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Kinetic data of the darkening and bleaching process of the photochromic spirooxazine embedded in ormosil solid matrices, and in solutions (THF and EtOH)

Samples	Bleaching in the dark $t_{1/2}/s$	Bleaching with vis light $t_{1/2}/s$	Darkening with UV light $t_{1/2}/s$
THF-Dye	20.4	12.5	14.6
EtOH-Dye	148	24.8	57
Ph-Dye	540	82	49
NH ₂ Ph-dye	1500	85	67
NH ₂ Ph-Dye-Zn ²⁺	>2.5 X 10 ⁸	3800	781

Fig. 5 Scheme of the possible formation of two zinc chelates of the spirooxazine during UV irradiation.

Fig. 6 Thermal stability of the coloured merocyanine molecules in the dark in NH_2Ph -modified ormosil matrices with and without zinc ions.

The coloration, however, can be “deleted” by irradiation with visible light, when the coloration is bleached, reverting the molecules back to their original colourless structure. The bleached samples keep their whiteness in the dark and can be coloured again by irradiation with UV-light (Fig. 7). This recording–erasing process is reversible and can be repeated by alternating UV and visible light irradiation.

The reversibility of the recording–erasing process of the photochromic coatings makes it possible to use them for optical data recording, as shown in Fig. 8. In order to show the feasibility of recording optical data in the coatings, a colourless sample was irradiated through a mask using UV light. The initials of the Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM) can be clearly seen in Fig. 8. The recorded data can be erased by irradiation with either UV or visible light, obtaining a fully coloured or fully bleached sample.

The thermal stability of the coloured form of the photochromic material was checked by storing the coloured films at room temperature in the dark for 15 days, showing no important changes (loss in colour < 4%) in the absorption spectra. The

Fig. 7 Full recording–erasing process of the photochromic coatings by alternating UV and visible light irradiation.

Fig. 8 Recording–erasing processes in a photochromic organic–inorganic hybrid coating exposed to UV or visible radiation through a mask.

Fig. 9 Fatigue resistance of thermally stable organic–inorganic hybrid material under alternate visible and UV light irradiation. In each cycle, the film was irradiated for 50 min. The absorbance was monitored at $1 \frac{1}{4}$ 554 nm.

incorporation of the NH_2Ph groups into the inner pore surface of the matrix promotes the stabilization of the coloured form of the spirooxazine, allowing the interaction between merocyanine and zinc ions and the formation of a coloured complex, which can be bleached by visible light.

For practical applications, high fatigue resistance is very important to achieve repeated processes of recording–erasing optical information. The fatigue resistance of the coatings was tested by performing recording–erasing cycles, showing no significant loss in colour for at least seven cycles (Fig. 9).

Conclusions

Novel photochromic coatings were designed showing remarkable coloured state/colourless state bistability in the dark. The coatings consist of a dispersion of a commercial spirooxazine in a sol–gel hybrid matrix. The stabilization of the coloured form of the dye molecules is reached by the incorporation of zinc ions that form a chelate with these photochromic molecules. The coatings acquire a purple colouration upon exposure to UV light,

which is stable in the dark. The coloured coatings do not undergo thermal bleaching in the dark, as the conventional photochromic materials do, and can only be reverted to their original colourless state by irradiation with visible light. This recording–erasing process is reversible and can, therefore, be repeated by alternating UV and visible light irradiation.

Taking into consideration the stability of the coloured and bleached states in the dark, the reversibility of the system, and their high fatigue resistance, the photochromic coatings prepared in this work can be proposed as promising candidates for the reversible storage of optical information in a thin-film (thickness $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.64 mm). Even though the coloration of the coatings in their coloured state is not very strong, and the bleaching–darkening processes are not fast enough for certain applications, the possibility of having a bistable photochromic material is of great importance as it opens new possibilities for the design of optical devices.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by research projects from MICINN (MAT2008-00010/NAN) and from CSIC (PIE-200860I074). The authors are grateful to PPG Industries Inc. for the generous donation of the photochromic molecule used in this work.

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